

Spin-offs from Homogeneous
Nucleation in Polymer Solutions
by John H. Jennings, M.S.
zenodo.org

key words

"homogeneous nucleation"

"polymer solutions"

"spin-offs"

rainfall

"space travel"

"polymer molecular weight"

SPIN-OFFS FROM HOMOGENEOUS
NUCLEATION IN POLYMER SOLUTIONS

ABSTRACT

The data and theory have been done for the problem of homogeneous nucleation in polymer solutions. The governing equation for this process is $T - T_0 = (3kT_0^2 w_2 MW_0) / (60 a_0 MW_2)$ and three uses have been found. In this article, the author will explain and outline the reasoning behind them. First, the above formula presents itself as a new way to measure molecular weight polymer, which will be developed in some detail. Second, this equation has implications for interstellar space travel, in that it says how a matter-antimatter reactor can be used for propulsion along with magnetic bottles that hold electrons and ~~anti~~ positrons after they have been captured. Third, by assuming that this starting equation derived from classical nucleation theory applies for gaseous "solution" $\rightarrow$ liquid H_2O droplets, then it only takes algebra to

Come up with a formula for onset of rain in clouds. This governing equation possibly has other applications and is different from boiling point elevation that requires a special thermometer to measure millidegrees.
 - five keywords -- see last page
 INTRODUCTION 3/10/22

A new theory can have multiple applications. The author did the math for the governing equation and saw three possible uses. In the next three sections, the spin-offs for Jennings' POLYMER RESEARCH JOURNAL [1] equation will be developed.

PETERMINATION OF MOLECULAR WEIGHT POLYMER

Now, boiling point elevation is used to measure molecular weight polymer BLACKMORE [2], but the effect is one more

of millidegrees Centigrade whereas for
 limit of superheat JENNINGS AND MIDDLEMAN
 there was an effect of 10-15 degrees
 Centigrade rise for 2000 and 4000 MW
 polystyrene in cyclohexane. [3]

I propose limit of superheat as a
 possible way to measure polymer MW.
 There would have to be a solvent such as
 cyclohexane (aliphatic), for example,
 cyclo^{pentane}~~hexane~~, heptane or ~~the~~ solvents of
 that nature that are completely miscible
 with various MW of polymer.

The column method is described in
 JENNINGS AND MIDDLEMAN but it is
 obvious that $\Delta T = T - T_0$ is inversely
 proportional to MW^2 , polymer molecular weight.

So, the column method where the rising droplet of polymer solution is super-heated to its limit is less able to distinguish MW of high polymer.

INTERSTELLAR SPACE TRAVEL

The author had an idea that electrons and antielectrons can be harvested by proper magnetic filters. In outer space, it could be that free electrons and free antielectrons are separated by Lieder frost layers. These two rotate in the opposite direction in a magnetic field and it ~~is later~~ has been shown that antimatter can be stored (see Ref. (12) in PHASE CHANGE AND SPACE

TRAVEL ~~(M)~~ [4]).

With ingenious engineering, the matter and antimatter can be made to propel the spacecraft. See (4) for a developed treatment.

SELECTION OF CLOUDS TO SEED FOR RAIN

The governing equation ~~can be~~ is assumed to apply in reverse, that is, instead of a polymer solution we posit an "solution" of atmospheric constituents plus water vapor. In contrast to a polymer solution super heating to give way to solvent bubbles, in a raincloud the gaseous solution supercools to critical sized raindroplets.

The resulting equation for this process is derived as IAJER [5], Equation (9) there, presented here,

$$T - T_0 = \left(\frac{3kT_0^2}{60a_0} \right) \left(\frac{P_{H_2O}^*}{P_{air}} \right) RH$$

Presumably this IAJER formula would enable people to identify candidate clouds for seeding with AgI, NaCl or dry ice. The ~~plane~~ airplane has instruments to measure T , P_{air} and RH. b_0 , a_0 and $P_{H_2O}^*$ can be calculated. It takes a computer to get T_0 , the dew point. Given that T is dropping down to T_0 , cloud-seeding can be done.

CONCLUSION

This very brief mini-review is intended to produce further study and interest in nucleation. It is important to determine molecular weight polymer. Man is looking to the stars, so conceivably the governing equation provides inspiration on how to fuel space travel. Since there is a problem with drought in various areas of the world, something has to be done to stimulate rain in the mountains.

REFERENCES

[1] [2] [3] [4] [5]

SPIN-OFFS REFERENCES

- "homogeneous nucleation" John H. Jennings
"polymer solutions"
"spin-offs" rainfall "space travel" "polymer
molecular weight"
- [1] JH Jennings, "Homogeneous^{molecular weight} Nucleation from Polymer Solutions"
POLYMERS RESEARCH JOURNAL;
Vol. 8, No. 4 pp.311-319 (2014).
- [2] Blackmore WR, "Ebulliometry and the determination of the molecular weights of polymers." Can. J. Chem, 1959; 37: 1508-1516.
- [3] Jennings JH, Middleman S. "Homogeneous nucleation of vapor from polymer solutions." Macromolecules, 1985; 18: 2274-2276.
- [4] Jennings, JH. "Phase change and space travel." ASIAN JOURNAL OF RESEARCH AND REVIEWS IN PHYSICS. 2021; 4(2): 48-51.
- [5] Jennings, JH. "The Dew Point as Nucleation Limit in a Cloud" IAJER. Vol. 4, Iss. 12 (December-2021), pp 01-03.